

Table 2. Effect of N on grain yield,^a Aduthurai, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	1.4 c
40	1.8 b
80	2.0 a
120	2.1 a

^aAverage of all varieties.

yield (Table 1). N level did not influence RTV, but significantly influenced grain yield. Highest yield was with 120 kg

N/ha, which was at par with yield at 80 kg N/ha (Table 2). N × varietal interaction was not significant. *ℓ*

The International Rice Research Newsletter and the IRRI Reporter are mailed free to qualified individuals and institutions engaged in rice production and training. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Seed dormancy in rice varieties

P. S. S. Murthy, plant physiologist; and M. D. Babu and S. S. R. Prasad, research assistants, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh, India

Dormancy of seeds within the same panicle varies with spikelet position on the panicle. We studied within-panicle dormancy patterns of 10 popular kharif rices at ARS in 1982 kharif. Panicles were collected at harvest and divided equally into top, middle, and bottom parts. They were sown in soil and watered as necessary.

Dormancy was lowest in the top 1/3

Seed dormancy at different spikelet levels within rice panicles, Maruteru, India.

Variety	Dormant seeds (%)			Variety	Dormant seeds (%)		
	Top	Middle	Bottom		Top	Middle	Bottom
MTU5293	50	60	90	MTU5182	40	70	90
MTU2716	40	70	90	MTU2400	40	70	90
MTU2077	60	50	90	BPT11503	50	70	80
MTU4569	40	70	90	PLA1100	50	70	80
MTU5201	40	65	95	Mean	46	66.5	88.5
MTU2067	50	70	80	CD (5%): V : ns		P = 3	V × P : ns
				CV (%): 15.3			

of panicles and gradually increased in the middle and bottom parts (see table). This was attributed to the different age of seeds at different panicle levels.

Anthesis and fertilization occur in an acropetal succession; therefore the top spikelets are fertilized earliest and are oldest. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

High yielding, semidwarf, blast (BI)-resistant NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 for southern Andhra Pradesh

G. V. Reddy, K. J. Reddy, V. D. Naidu, M. Gopinath, and M. R. K. Reddy, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station, Nellore 524004, India

NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 were developed for B1 resistance and suitable grain quality for southern Andhra Pradesh. NLR9672-96 is a secondary selection from NLR9672, from Bulk H/9 and Milekkunning. NLR27999 was selected from a segregating generation of RP31-49-2/BCP 1. Milekkunning and RP31-49-2 were parents for B1

Table 1. Yield attributes of NLR9672-96 and NLR27999, Nellore, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	1000-grain weight (g)
NLR27999	160-170	113	289	291	22
NLR9672-96	150-160	119	282	301	21
NLR9672	150-160	100	248	339	23
NLR9674	160-170	104	269	326	22

resistance. NLR9672-96 matures in 150-160 d and NLR27999 in 160-170 d. Both are weakly photoperiod sensitive and have short, bold grains with dirty brown glumes. Milled rice is white and translucent, and meets local consumer requirements. Threshability of both varieties is good, and both shed fewer

grains than locally grown NLR9672. Both have seed dormancy at maturity and lodging resistance. NLR9672-96 has a droopy flag leaf and NLR27999 an erect, medium flag leaf.

The varieties are moderately resistant to leaf and neck B1 and bacterial blight and resistant to brown planthopper.

NLR27999 can be planted as late as October without yield reduction. Both varieties yield better than local varieties, even when 60-d-old seedlings are planted. They have good tillering ability, and a high number of panicles/m², and grains/panicle. The 1,000-grain weight is similar and slightly less than that of local varieties (Table 1).

NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 were evaluated in replicated kharif varietal, multilocation, and minikit trials from 1981 to 1984. Check varieties were locally popular NLR9672 and NLR9674. The new rices yielded significantly more than the checks (Table 2). In 1983 trials at 5 sites,

Table 2. Performance of NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 at Nellore, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)						
	1981	1982	1983	1984	1983 (MLT)	1984 (MLT)	1984 (MT)
NLR27999	4.3	5.6	—	6.5	6.2	5.1	5.3
NLR9672-96	—	—	3.8	6.5	—	5.6	5.4
NLR9672	3.7	4.8	3.4	—	5.5	4.8	4.3
NLR9674	3.8	5.5	2.6	4.0	—	4.6	—
CD	0.23	0.25	0.19	0.35	—	0.38	—
CV%	4.0	3.24	15.0	11.24	—	16.08	—

^aMLT = multilocation trial, mean of 5 locations; MT = minikit trial, mean of 4 locations.

NLR27999 yielded an average 13% more than NLR9672. In 1984, NLR27999 yielded 6% more and NLR9672-96 17% more than NLR9672.

In minikit trials, NLR27999 yielded 23% more and NLR9672-96 25% more than NLR9672. The new varieties are becoming popular with farmers. *ℵ*

Abnormal spikelet on IR58

M. Komatsu, Japan Overseas Cooperation Volunteers, Meralco Corporate Farm Management, Inc., San Mateo, Isabela, Philippines

IR58 developed 10-70% abnormal spikelets in the Jun-Sep 1984 crop in Isabela, Philippines. Incidence was highest in San Mateo, Kauayan, and Ramon municipalities. Spikelets remained open after flowering and had the following shapes: the tip of the palea and lemma bent inward; an extra lemma developed on the base outside the palea; there was no palea; the palea was malformed and the lemma was torn in two; the lemma had two awns and no palea (see figure). Flowering and ovary development seemed normal, but the

External shape of abnormal spikelet. Isabela, Philippines.

abnormal spikelets bore empty or tapering grains.

Transplanting began in late June. Days were cloudy and rain often fell before sunset. Day temperature was 30-33° C, and night temperature 27-30° C.

Lowest temperature was 25° C. Days were sunny when panicles began to form in mid-Aug.

No other varieties had abnormal spikelets. In 1985 dry season, few farmers planted IR58. *ℵ*

Reaction of rices to natural infection of leaf scald (LSc)

Syharuddin Rahamma, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops (MORIF), South Sulawesi, Indonesia

LSc caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* is one of the most important wet season rice diseases in South Sulawesi. It caused serious losses on variety Bakka in 1976 in Gowa and Takalar districts and IR36 and IR50 in 1981-82 wet season at Maros Research Station.

Response of 10 cultivars to natural infection of LSc, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Variety	Score ^a
Bahagia	1
BR51-114-3-2-1	1
BR168-2B-23	1
BR189-103-2-1-4-2-1	1
CR1002	1
DV85	1
IR9101-37-1	1
IR92 17-58-2-2	1
IR15314-30-3-1-3	1
IR15429-268-1	1
IR8192-200-3-3-1-1 (resistant check)	3
IR36 (susceptible check)	8

^a1980 Standard evaluation system for rice 1-9 scale.

In 1983-84 we evaluated 100 cultivars for reaction to natural LSc infection under lowland conditions and 90-60-0 kg applied NPK/ha. Two rows of 10 plants of each test variety were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Two rows of resistant IR8 192-200-3-3-1-1 and susceptible IR36 were planted after every 10 test varieties.

Forty-six varieties had some resistance. Ten varieties had resistance scores 1 to 3. Resistant check IR8192-200-3-3-1-1 scored 3 (see table). *ℵ*